

Role of muscarinic acetylcholine receptor M1 in the cardiovascular system

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ABSTRACT

Muscarinic acetylcholine receptors (mAChRs) are G-protein-coupled receptors mainly activated *via* the parasympathetic pathway. These receptors are widely known to mediate functions within both central and peripheral nervous system, activated by the neurotransmitter acetylcholine (ACh). Well known studies suggested the contribution of ACh in regulating cardiovascular functions *via* various pathways; however, the role of mAChRs was limited to the AChM2R, AChM3R, and AChM4R subtypes. In contrast, AChM1R subtype has not been sufficiently studied in the cardiovascular system due to its abundance in the central nervous system and its implication in many physiological and pathological brain functions. Recently, studies revealed the presence of AChM1R in the cardiovascular system directly using knockout models, or indirectly treating with AChM1R selective agonist/antagonist. This mini-review aims to summarize recent findings in the role of AChM1R in cardiovascular function and diseases.

KEYWORDS: muscarinic receptor, cardiovascular, heart, vasculature, AChM1R, acetylcholine.

INTRODUCTION

The cardiovascular system facilitates blood flow and nutrient uptake throughout the body, while the

components of the cardiovascular system including the heart, arteries, veins, and capillaries work together to maintain homeostasis. Defects in the cardiovascular system lead to severe cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) including heart failure, hypertension, arrhythmias, carditis, congenital heart disease, stroke, venous thrombosis, and peripheral artery disease, just to name a few [1]. CVDs also include coronary artery diseases (CAD), including angina and myocardial infarction. In 2016, the American College of Cardiology reported 840,768 deaths resulting from CVDs, marking them as the leading cause of death in the United States [2]. The underlying mechanisms of CVDs may vary, but many share overlapping components. As such, the presence of widely localized pharmacological targets in the cardiovascular system such as adrenergic receptors, innervated by epinephrine or norepinephrine, as well as cholinergic receptors, innervated by acetylcholine, constantly inspire cardiovascular researchers to investigate therapeutic solutions for these deadly complications.

Many physiological functions throughout the body are directly or indirectly mediated by the secretion of acetylcholine (ACh). ACh is synthesized from choline and acetyl coenzyme A when acetyltransferase is present and its function is mediated by either muscarinic or nicotinic acetylcholine receptors [3, 4]. Unlike nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChR), which function as short acting ligand-gated ion channels, muscarinic acetylcholine receptors (mAChRs) are G protein-

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coupled receptors that produce longer-lasting effects. Importantly, the cholinergic muscarinic receptors act within the autonomic nervous system, coordinating tissues such as smooth muscles. Because mAChRs are characterized by their long acting effects, they, along with the adrenergic pathway, are more efficient in treating serious conditions such as CVDs, which require prolonged action [5]. Five unique subtypes belong to the muscarinic receptors' family - AChM1R-M5, with AChM1R, M5 and M4 being highly expressed in the central nervous system (CNS). AChM3R is found predominantly in the vascular system and smooth muscles while AChM2R is localized to the heart. Many studies also demonstrated both, the presence and abundance of specific mAChR subtypes in the cardiovascular system such as AChM1R, AChM2R, and AChM3R [6-8]. AChM1R has also been reported in the cardiomyocytes of the atria and the ventricles, suggesting an important role in cardiac function [9].

Despite only few studies focused on the contribution of AChM1R in the cardiovascular system due to its abundance in the CNS, the aim of this review is to provide an overview of the role of AChM1R in the cardiovascular system, opening the possibility to developing therapeutic targets for cardiovascular complications.

AChM1R in the vascular system

The cardiovascular system function has been found to be regulated by many mAChR subtypes. For many years, the cardiovascular system was thought to be partially regulated by the AChM2R until recent studies confirmed the presence of other mAChR subtypes in the vasculature. The distribution and localization of the AChM1R in the vasculature including arteries, veins and the endothelium has been widely reported [6]. AChM1R is shown to be more specific for the pulmonary vascular endothelium [10, 11]. A study reported AChM1R and AChM3R to mediate endothelium-dependent vasodilation, based almost solely on pharmacological studies using the AChM1R antagonist pirenzepine. In addition, AChM1R has been suggested to be involved in a variety of cholinergic vasorelaxations in rat carotid arteries, human pulmonary and canine lingual arteries, and the perforating branch of the human internal mammary artery [10, 12-14]. Notably, AChM3Rs are

unquestionably known for their vasodilation properties within vascular smooth muscle cells, but there are reports that claim AChM1R plays a small, yet significant, role in this as well. A study using canine lingual arteries revealed that AChM1Rs play a role in mediating vasodilation, alongside of, but to a lesser extent than, AChM3Rs [12]. A study on myocardial blood flow redistribution, once again using pirenzepine and canine subendocardial blood vessels, found that AChM1R coronary receptors may be responsible for the redistribution of blood flow to the sub-endocardium during cholinergic coronary vasodilation [15]. In addition, a study using sheep and, once again, pirenzepine also showed that cholinergic vasorelaxation in the coronary arteries may be mediated by endothelial AChM1Rs [16]. Other studies seemingly confirmed that ACh-induced vasodilatation is at least partially mediated by AChM1Rs, because of reduced vasodilatation associated with pirenzepine administration (Figure 1) [17, 18].

AChM1Rs, in conjunction with AChM3Rs, are thought to be involved in vasorelaxation within pulmonary arteries. A study focused on the role of AChM1Rs and AChM3Rs specifically in human pulmonary arteries, found that both, ACh and AChM1R agonists, McN-A-343 and PD142505, relaxed human isolated pulmonary arteries that had been previously constricted with noradrenaline. In addition, in situations where the endothelium had been removed, ACh still caused constriction, but the AChM1R agonists did not. These results indicate that along with AChM3R, AChM1R is involved in the endothelium-dependent ACh-induced relaxation of human pulmonary arteries [10]. Other studies using pirenzepine have implicated AChM1Rs in more of a vasoconstrictive role or found that it plays no role at all [16, 19]. Despite this evidence, the role of AChM1Rs in endothelium-dependent vasodilation has long since been argued. In contrast, other studies using a wide variety of animal species showed that AChM3Rs mediates the cholinergic dilation of coronary arteries, with insignificant influence from AChM1Rs [18, 20-22]. These conflicting reports may be due in part to the antagonists used, which, while selective, still have high affinities for the off-target muscarinic subtypes, such as AChM3Rs. Recent studies using knockout mice show strong evidence that AChM1Rs are not

Figure 1. Role of AChM1R in ACh-induced vasodilation. ACh binds and activate AChM1R on the endothelial cell membrane which activates the effector Phospholipase C (PLC). That will lead to the production of diacylglycerol (DAG) and Inositol triphosphate (IP3). IP3 will initiate Ca²⁺ release from the ER; the elevation in intracellular Ca²⁺ will result in the activation of endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS). Phosphorylation of eNOS will lead to the production of nitric oxide (NO) from L-arginine in the vascular smooth muscle cells.

involved in cholinergic responses in their tested vascular sections [23]. In a slightly different take on the subject, one study showed that AChM1Rs and AChM3Rs on perivascular nerves, but not vascular smooth muscle, were responsible for ACh-induced endothelium-independent vasodilations, and calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP)-containing nerve (CGRPergic)-mediated vasodilations [6, 24]. This suggests that mAChRs, mainly AChM1R subtypes, are expressed in rat mesenteric arteries, and that the activation of AChM1Rs and AChM3Rs on CGRPergic nerves releases CGRP, which causes endothelium-independent vasodilatation [6].

AChM1R in the heart

As mentioned previously, the role and localization of AChM1Rs in the heart has not been sufficiently

studied. In contrast, ACh2MR has been shown to play an important role in the cardiac muscle. Interestingly, several studies reported the coexistence of AChM1Rs and AChM2Rs specifically in the adult rat's heart. A study noted that the AChM1Rs' and AChM2Rs' messages were amplified as seen from total mRNA levels, whereas AChM3Rs', AChM4Rs', and AChM5Rs' mRNA was not. Immunofluorescence studies also detected the presence of AChM1Rs in these adult rat ventricular myocytes [25]. Another study demonstrated the presence of AChM1Rs in the ventricles of the rat's heart and they were able to determine that the majority of the mAChR were of the AChM1R subtype while AChM2R subtype was exclusively in the atria [26]. Recently, the presence of AChM1R coupled with Gq proteins was shown in the mammalian myocardium [27].

These results suggest an essential role of AChM1R in the heart and in the mechanism of decreasing heart rate.

AChM1R in pulmonary arteries

It is worth mentioning that AChM1Rs have been reported to play a major role in the pulmonary arteries. AChM1Rs are at the core of pulmonary circulation and their expression in the pulmonary vascular endothelium carries extensive evidence [10, 28, 29]. Studies have also demonstrated the endothelium dependency for vasodilatation. Apart from vasodilatation, AChM1Rs were previously shown to mediate vasoconstriction in rabbits and that this pressor response is endothelium dependent [28]. These studies show that AChM1Rs play a major role in the pulmonary arteries as compared to other small arteries and blood vessels. Endothelium dependency for vasodilatation is highly disputed as there are reports suggesting that it is not entirely required for mediating vasodilatation. One particular report has shown that intact endothelium is not absolutely necessary for mediating vasodilatation in rat mesenteric arteries [6]. Another study reported that the relaxation induced by ACh in the blood vessels is due to the activation of AChM1Rs on endothelial cells in isolated human pulmonary veins [29]. These findings suggest a significant role AChM1Rs may play in the process of vasodilation in pulmonary arteries.

AChM1R-mediated signaling cascades

Understanding the signaling mechanisms mediated by receptor activation will allow for a better targeting of signaling components that are perturbed during disease states. AChM1Rs belong to the G-protein coupled receptors (GPCR), which are the largest family of transmembrane proteins in mammals, with a cascade of events leading to intracellular change [30]. Such changes occur through exogenous or endogenous ligand stimulation. Activation of the receptors allows for the regulation of different areas of function within the body. There are many different types of GPCRs and they can be divided into different classes: class A (rhodopsin-like), class B (secretin receptor-like), class C (metabotropic glutamate/pheromone), class D (fungal mating pheromone receptor), class E (cyclic AMP receptors), and class F (frizzled/smoothened) [31]. The classes differ based on two main criteria:

1) amino acid sequences, and 2) location and nature of orthosteric binding site/ligand [32].

The AChM1R is a member of the class A receptors, which is the largest class of rhodopsin-like proteins. This class utilizes light, neurotransmitters, and hormones as ligands to initiate intracellular change. Because of the subunits involved in the pathway, AChM1R is also classified as a Gq GPCR. Gq is activated to stimulate phosphoinositide-specific phospholipase C β (PLC- β) and the generation of inositol-triphosphate (IP $_3$) and 1,2-diacylglycerol (DAG) [1]. This pathway is important for the contraction of the cardiac myocytes [33]. The Gq-coupled AChM1Rs in vascular smooth muscle cells are needed to initiate contractions in the blood vessels. This pathway is stimulated by a ligand, either endogenous (i.e. ACh) or exogenous (i.e. an agonist of ACh) [30]. The first step in the AChM1R pathway is the binding of the ligand to the receptor, which causes the activation of the heterotrimeric Gq protein complex [34]. The type of effectors which are stimulated depends on the type of G protein activated. This protein complex attached to the receptor intracellularly is comprised of a G α -bound to GDP, G β - and G γ -subunits. However, once it is activated, the subunits will break off from the receptor with the α -subunit replacing the GDP with GTP, dissociating the complex into a G α -GTP and G $\beta\gamma$ -subunits [35]. Each subunit interacts with secondary messengers along its cascade. The G α -GTP unit activates phospholipase C (PLC- β), which then cleaves phosphatidylinositol-4,5 bisphosphate (PIP $_2$) into IP $_3$ and DAG [35]. In the endoplasmic reticulum, there are calcium reserves that are regulated by IP $_3$ receptors. The synthesis of IP $_3$ results in the reserves being opened, stimulating the release of calcium into the cell [8]. This intracellular calcium activates calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase II (CAMKII) and subsequently activates the myosin light chain kinase (MLCK) [33]. This final effector is the trigger for the vascular smooth muscle cells to contract, which is the desired effect of the pathway [36]. The DAG generated and the increased calcium concentration will activate protein kinase C (PKC) [37]. The intracellular effect continues until the GTP in the G α -GTP subunit is hydrolyzed back to GDP, converting to its inactive state by returning to the muscarinic receptor and binding to the G $\beta\gamma$ -subunit once again (Figure 2) [35].

Figure 2. ACh-induced contraction in smooth muscle cells. Binding of ACh to AChM1R activates PLC followed by both IP₃ and DAG. Activation will result in an increase in intracellular Ca²⁺ and activation of calcium/calmodulin kinase II. Myosin light chain kinase will be activated, and contraction occurs.

Interestingly, dysregulation of certain components in the signaling pathway has been reported to be associated with several cardiovascular complications. G α_q activity can be influenced by the concentration of PLC β_1 . Over-expression of G α_q in mice has been used to assess its role in cardiac hypertrophy which refers to the thickening/enlargement of the heart muscle. Furthermore, it was observed that the greater the level of G α_q expression, the quicker the onset of decompensated heart failure. Thus, it appears that even though G α_q overexpression produces a unique compromised type of cardiomyopathy that is neither compensated or decompensated, it can progress to classic decompensation with the superimposition of hemodynamic stress [38]. Reduced AChM1R responses may also result from a loss of downstream signal transduction elements. For example, prolonged activation of human AChM1R or AChM3R in Chinese hamster ovary (CHO) cells not only induce AChMRs' down-regulation, but also accelerate degradation of G α_q /11 protein [39]. However, inhibiting G α_q signaling may be an approach to prevent cardiac hypertrophy through pressure overload stimuli. G α_q receptor

coupling *via* several extracellular signals directly stimulates the hypertrophic response, but there are clearly other cell signaling systems unrelated to G α_q that play a role in the development of hypertrophy. Furthermore, it can be inferred that G α_q signaling, independent of hemodynamic load, leads to contractile dysfunction at the myocyte level.

Contraction of smooth muscle defines the lumen in blood vessels, airways, intestine, uterus and bladder. An abnormal increase in smooth muscle tone has been implicated in the pathogenesis of hypertension, cardiogenic shock and pyloric stenosis. The principal mechanisms that initiate smooth muscle contraction are the rise of intracellular free Ca²⁺ concentration and/or increased sensitivity of the contractile apparatus towards Ca²⁺ [40].

Role of AChM1R in cardiovascular diseases

AChM1Rs have been shown to play a role in many cardiovascular diseases such as chronic atrial fibrillation, myocardial ischemia, and angina pectoris [41, 42]. Selective AChM1R antagonist, pirenzepine, has been suggested as a potential treatment for effort-induced myocardial ischemia.

In addition, the parasympathomimetic activity of pirenzepine is being explored as a potential drug target for treating angina pectoris [42]. Vagal tone depression predicts a poor outcome following a myocardial infarction. In the past, some studies have reported that selective AChM1R- antagonist, pirenzepine, when given orally, was able to significantly increase the indices of cardiac vagal activity. It was then suggested that pirenzepine may have the potential to prevent malignant ventricular arrhythmias following an infarction [43]. Another study noted an upregulation of the AChM1R receptor mRNA alongside an upregulated AChM3R mRNA which can contribute to an increased signaling through the Gq pathway as seen in Congestive Heart Failure (CHF) [44]. All the above have demonstrated a strong evidence for the role of AChM1R subtypes in cardiovascular diseases and have paved way for exploring potential new therapeutic targets.

Transcription factors involved in AChM1R and cardiovascular functions

In the rat and human genomes, five subtypes of the muscarinic receptor have been identified. While the coding sequences of all five genes are in a single exon, their structures 5' of the initiation codon remain largely unknown with the exception of AChM4R [45]. AChM1R has been thought to participate in behavior, stress-adaptive cardiovascular functions, and blood pressure regulation. M1 promoter sequences are similar to those of the M4 muscarinic receptor gene in that they occur in a GC-rich region and do not have a TATA box [46]. However, there are two potential CAAT boxes and several possible transcription factors that may bind to the promoter sequence, including SP1 and AP-1-3 [47]. Interestingly, several studies have implicated Sp1 in cardiovascular disorders. Studies have shown that regulating human SERCA gene expression in cardiomyocytes is dependent on transactivation events initiated by Sp1 and Sp3 [48]. The antifibrotic mechanism of miR-7a/b has also been studied in ANG II-treated cardiac fibroblasts. Based on their findings, miR-7a/b plays an antifibrotic role in ANG II-treated CFs *via* the Sp1 pathway. AP-1 is shown to be involved in endothelial cell differentiation, blood vessel formation, and cardiomyocyte proliferation, and

protrusion into the injured area [49]. The above-mentioned findings can possibly open new role for AChM1R in the cardiovascular function.

AChM1R distribution in other tissues

Mucosal cilia

AChM1Rs have been reported in many different tissues in the body. For instance, muco-ciliary clearance protects airways against inhaled xenobiotics, and ciliated cells are known to propel mucus and particles by the coordinated beating of their cilia. ACh is known to increase ciliary beat frequency (CBF), and increased CBF is believed to increase muco-ciliary transport [50, 51]. ACh is the main transmitter of parasympathetic nerve fibers in the airways, but it can also be released from the bronchial epithelium and immune system cells [52, 53]. Once released, ACh induces cilia-stimulatory effects *via* the mAChRs. A study using muscarinic knockout mice measured muco-ciliary transport speed in the absence of AChM1Rs, AChM2Rs, and AChM3Rs [54]. The study used AChM1R^{-/-}, AChM3R^{-/-} and AChM2R₃R^{-/-} knockout mice, and particle transport speed was measured using Dynabeads and microscopy. The results showed that while AChM3Rs stimulate cilia-driven particle transport, and AChM2Rs inhibit it, AChM1Rs increase cilia-driven particle transport in the absence of both AChM2Rs and AChM3Rs, in a sort of backup system [54].

Renal fibrosis

AChM1Rs may play an indirect role in renal fibrosis when they activate cytoplasmic proline-rich tyrosine kinase-2 (Pyk2) through unknown means [55]. Studies have shown that mechanical stretch, and the resultant renal tubular distension, could lead to renal fibrosis. Experiments with renal tubular epithelial cells revealed that mechanical stretch induces reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can activate Pyk2. Pyk2 is a member of the focal adhesion kinase (FAK) family and is expressed in tubular epithelial cells when activated by stimuli. Researchers further explored Pyk2 by using Pyk2^{-/-} mice and found that transforming growth factor-β1 (TGF-β1) induced by mechanical stretch was significantly reduced, as was the expression of connective tissue growth factor (CTGF). Expression of CTGF is independent of TGF-β1, but dependent

on the Rho-associated coiled-coil forming protein kinase (ROCK1) pathway. Taken together, the evidence suggests that Pyk2 could be an initiating factor in renal fibrosis [56].

Novel selective AChM1R antagonists in different diseases

Many studies have reported the synthetic strategies and biological characterization of novel AChM1R antagonists in different complications. One particular study reported the synthesis of many novel long-acting antagonists of mAChRs; they showed that 4-hexyloxy derivatives of 1-[2-(4-oxidobenzoyloxy)ethyl]-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridin-1-ium are highly selective to the AChM1Rs, suggesting its role in complications related to the presence of AChM1Rs subtype such as striatal cholinergic dystonia, delaying epileptic seizure after organophosphate intoxication or even relieving depression [57]. Another class of compounds containing diaryl amide groups has also been reported to possess AChM1R antagonistic properties. This study showed that a compound, VU0433670, is a potent AChM1R antagonist as identified using structure activity relationship (SAR) studies with possibility to be tested in several complications including CNS pathologies and cardiopathies [58]. Apart from being a potential treatment strategy for Parkinson's and cardiovascular diseases, it has been shown that mAChR antagonists can also be used as chemotherapeutic agents. One study reported the chemotherapeutic potential of a Penehyclidine hydrochloride (PHC) derivative, R2HBJJ which has been demonstrated to depress the growth of small cell lung cancers (SCLCs), thus opening new avenues for the use of mAChR antagonists in cancer treatment. This compound, R2HBJJ showed more selectivity to AChM1R and AChM3R subtypes further exemplifying the therapeutic potential of selective AChM1R antagonists [59]. Another study recently characterized the chemical constituents of the Chinese medicinal plant, *Scopolia tangutica* (*S.tangutica*) and identified a particularly potent AChM1R antagonist N1,N10-di-dihydrocaffeoylspermidine, which displayed a 15-fold selectivity for AChM1Rs over AChM3Rs Du, Liu, Zhang, Wang, Zhao, He, Zhou, Mei and Liang [60]. These studies suggest that more novel selective AChM1R antagonists are being developed, with absolute necessity for testing the compounds

that already showed significant selectivity for AChM1R against cardiovascular diseases in the future.

CONCLUSION

The cholinergic system plays an important role in the control of various autonomic functions in the cardiovascular system. Treatments targeting the adrenergic receptors such as β or α blockers have been widely prescribed to treat a variety of cardiovascular diseases. Muscarinic receptor subtypes such as AChM1R, AChM2R, and AChM3R have been reported in major organs that regulate cardiovascular function. In addition, several studies reported novel mAChRs' modulators as potential therapeutic targets for various disorders including cardiovascular pathologies. Based on the information presented in this mini-review, the time has arrived for muscarinic modulators to be sufficiently investigated for their potential involvement in cardiovascular diseases.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

No conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise, are declared by the authors.

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